

MEMORY AND RHETORIC IN THE ANCIENT AGE

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Sérgio Rodrigues de Souza

Philosopher. Doctor in Pedagogical Sciences. Post-Doctorate in Social Psychology.

Email: srgrodriguesdesouza@gmail.com.

Ana Rita César Lustosa

Degree in Visual Arts. Master in Art from the Federal University of Espírito Santo.

Email: lustosaanarita@gmail.com.

ABSTRACT

This essay aims to present reflections on memory and rhetoric in ancient times. This is a bibliographic study, based on analytical hermeneutics. As a methodology, for the accomplishment of this study, the analyzes were carried through researches in books, considering the main aspects and approaches on the rhetoric and the influence of the memory in the ancient period, in terms of politics and religion. It was not about speaking well, it was something far beyond that, the speaker should sing the sacred songs and hymns, the prayers obeying the same original phonetic metrics with which they were created. It was a mnemonic discipline that had never been seen and experienced, with such rigor and obedience to canonical principles at any other time in human history. Memory was linked to rhetoric by the fact that there was a whole cult directed to the gods, to the dead, and they complained that all discourse followed a very straight line, in terms of phonetic and linguistic ordering. Memory and rhetoric have always been together, because every good orator and rhetorician must automatically possess a high degree of mnemonic capacity, which he generally possesses, because when preparing for an oral exposition, a rigorous argumentation, he must memorize, not just excerpts, but a whole collection of works and the respective contexts [semantic, epistemic, philosophical, sociological, syntactic] in which they are found, as well as how they can weave a decent concatenated dialogue with the present reality.

Keywords: Memory. Rhetoric. Old age. Policy. Religion.

INTRODUCTION

Memory and rhetoric represent two paradigms of Antiquity, because the idea we have of ancient peoples, sometimes as having a very advanced culture, sometimes as barbarians who always fought with weapons is an idiosyncrasy created by Hollywood and cinema in general .

One thing for them was sacred, victory and defeat, and for this to come true in a field like rhetoric, the debaters would have to prove themselves skilled in verbal combat and have a good memory, in order to recite cases that occurred as empirical examples, during the defense of your theses.

Many speakers traveled from various places in Greece to the most important city of the Greek Empire, Athens, in order to present their speech skills, giving rise to rhetoric and, consequently, the art of rhetoric.

Reboul (1998) will say that rhetoric is only exercised in situations of uncertainty and conflict, in which the truth is not given and may never be achieved, except in the form of verisimilitude. This causes rhetorical arguments to be based on fierce defenses.

MEMORY AND RHETORIC

Memory and rhetoric were closely linked in the religious processes of the Ancient Age. What remains for us to clarify is why this link existed between one and the other and the answer may be that the speaker was not only pre-required to speak well and with extreme eloquence, clarity of exposition, tonality and fluency; he had to follow an entire ritual, using all his mnemonic potential, because this was a sacred and, at the same time, political requirement: the entire protection of the city, fertility, security, victories in wars depended on this sacred rite. political.

Having briefly explained this presentation about why memory and rhetoric are so linked, we are left to know how memory and rhetoric occurred in the Ancient Age; What elements were promoting this bond so efficiently?

Regarding memory, this work will not treat it as the ability to remember elements of the past, rather as a way that the ancients used to faithfully record and reproduce sacred magical formulas. Fustel de Coulanges reports that, if during a funeral repast, a public ceremony, the priest, by chance, slipped, he would have to repeat exactly this act in the following section and in all the others, because this incident was a divine determination, therefore, should be incorporated into the ritual and the apprentice should learn to perform it, in the same way. This is how the author explains, regarding the rites to mitigate the wrath of the gods, in which every detail of the prayer and movements had to be followed exactly, because men counted little on their friendship; soon,

The prayer, composed of such words, had managed to be answered; which, without a doubt, happened because it had been heard by the divinity, it had acted upon it, it had been powerful, more powerful than the god himself, who had not known how to resist. Therefore, the sacred terms of this mysterious prayer were preserved. After his father, his son started to repeat it. When the alphabet appeared, they began to write it. Every family, at least every religious family, had a book that contained the formulas that the ancestors used, and which the gods had heeded. It was a weapon that man used against the fickleness of the gods. But, not a single word, not a syllable, nor, above all, the rhythm to which it should be sung should be changed, because then the prayer would lose its strength (...). In vain, the most fervent hearts offered fat victims to the gods; if one of the innumerable rites of sacrifice were neglected, it would become null and void. The slightest fault made a sacred act a sacrilegious act. The slightest alteration disturbed and upset the religion of the country, and transformed the protective gods into so many cruel enemies (COULANGES, 2006, pp. 260-2).

The author presents that, even with the emergence of writing, memory cannot be put into disuse, because there were details of the ceremony that were not recorded yet and that proved to be crucial for the purpose of the celebration, which was to appease anger and volatile mood of the gods, whether domestic or municipal. For us, men educated in writing, whose enormous content of knowledge can be found in memories located in the media clouds and in books, it seems strange that there was a time in which men should carry in their memory all the knowledge that they needed to use immediately. .

In the ancient world and even in the era of the 2nd Industrial Revolution, most of the great men we hear about or read about did not know how to write or read; therefore, they should memorize all the knowledge necessary for their life in society. If, in relation to their needs, memory was a condition of life or death, in the context of rhetoric it was the fundamental factor, because without memory the speaker would be nothing.

Today, memory is the point to which manuals pay least attention when the topic is rhetoric, on the one hand, because the study of memory remains in limbo, on the other hand, after the invention of writing, memory was relegated to the background in art of rhetoric.

The priest Plato, the Harlot of Athens, considered memory as a defining element of man; for this reason he vehemently attacked the invention of writing, as he believed it would destroy memory:

When they arrived at writing, Thoth said: "This art, dear king, will make the Egyptians wiser and strengthen their memory; therefore, with writing I invented a great aid for memory and wisdom . " Tammuz replies: "Great artist Thoth! It is not the same thing to invent an art and judge the usefulness or harm that will come to those who practice it. You, as the father of writing, expect from it with your enthusiasm precisely the opposite of what it can do. Such a thing will make men forgetful, for they will cease to cultivate their

memory; trusting only in written books, they will only remember a subject outwardly and through signs, and not in themselves. Therefore, you did not invent an aid for memory, but only for remembering [...]” (PLATÃO, 2006 , 274e – 275b).⁴

Thus, we know that for this priest, the destruction of memory would be the destruction of the man himself, because this was his own memory, which would be united to him inseparably making them good.

The priest Plato, the Harlot of Athens, casts doubt on the capacity of memory (the Mother of the Muses) to recover all experiences, as we can see in his monologue Theaetetus, that he compares memory to a piece of wax in which a certain print. He added that it would not be a reliable copy of these experiences, so the memory would be closer to fantasy and imagination:

We can consider it, then, as a gift from Memory, the mother of the Muses. We make impressions upon it of whatever we wish to remember among the things we have seen or heard or thought of ourselves; we hold the wax under our perceptions and thoughts and take a seal from them, just as we take the marks from signet rings. Whatever is impressed on the wax, we remember and know as long as the image remains on the wax; everything that is obliterated or cannot be printed, we forget and do not know (PLATO, 1921, 191d).⁵

One of the studies that came down to us on memory was the treatise *On Memory* by the priest Aristotle, the Egotatra, in which he tried to describe it, but did not bother to point out its main elements. The lack of concern with memorization was also a concern in later antiquity, as we can see the priest Cicero, the Christian, railing against the carelessness to which it had been relegated.

Memory is a primordial factor, for a good condition and pre-existence of rhetoric, because the speaker needs to remember remarkable passages, thought during the elaboration of his speech and express them, using the instruments depending on the previous analysis of his speech. public, adapting them in whatever way is convenient, since their interest is in convincing or entertaining the public about their theories. This is characterized as a situation that persisted for centuries to come, because even though, nowadays , people resort to writing to remember letters, the phonetic arrangement is still a cognitive condition, impossible to be transcribed in its entirety. What is transcribed is an approximation translated into bass, treble, voice inflections, among other things; However, the intrinsic tonality is an experience that is

⁴PLATO. *Phaedrus* , 274e–275b.

⁵PLATEAU. *Theaetetus* , 191d.

unique and non-transferable, dependent on the health condition and conservation of memory to occur fully .

Most rhetoric manuals present its five canons: invention, disposition, elocution, memory and action (method of presenting the speech); Of all these canons, memory is the most important, despite being the least studied;

In Antiquity, before the existence of writing, the speaker's work was more complex, because he had to remember the entire ritual that had been learned and apprehended, in all its details, paying attention to every smallest detail required by the gods, in time of your presentation: it never hurts to remember that Homer's poems, the *Iliad* and the *Odyssey* , had 15,500 and 12,000 verses, respectively, while Hesiod's poems, the *Theogony* and *The Works and the Days* , had 1000 and 800 verses , each.

So, it was not about speaking well, it was something much more than that, the speaker had to sing the sacred songs and hymns, the prayers obeying the same original phonetic meter with which they were created. It was a mnemonic disciplinization that had never been seen or experienced, with such rigor and obedience to canonical principles, at any other time in human history.

This work is justified by carrying out a descriptive analysis of this procedure and the foundations that marked it, which can greatly contribute to the growth of the scientific framework, by presenting the correlational aspect between the historical and political context that marks this situation. It should be clarified that, in Antiquity, there was no Secular State, as religion and politics represented a single element, with disputes over the possession of power and its intrigues, public and private, as occurs whenever we have priests and politicians defending their interests.

Regarding the social relevance presented by such clarification, it applies to the point of clarifying to the broad public that, there was a moment in human history when memory was overvalued, and this gift was not extended to everyone; but only to those who had been chosen to represent the sacred curia. A whole study ritual was carried out from a very young age, for the apprentice to train his mnemonic condition to the extreme.

Memory was linked to rhetoric through the action that there was an entire cult directed to the gods, to the dead and they demanded that all speech followed a very straight line, with regard to phonetic and linguistic orders. Prayers, prayers, songs, sayings, all had to obey the same rites of variability of tones and timbres, just as they were created and presented to the gods, in their first time. Thus, with each generation of new priests they had to remember every detail, under penalty of awakening divine wrath against themselves and the people. The ancients

did not know the *self*, because for them there was only the *us*, in other words they did not separate the private from the public. The elements responsible for this very close link between memory and rhetoric were the religious cult dedicated to the manes and the domestic and municipal gods, who demanded it as such and were extremely angry, wrathful, vengeful: the gods never took revenge for offenses upon a single citizen, they punished the entire society.

writing had not yet developed, Priests, Kings, Poets, Orators, Masters, Reciters had to save all information, texts, choruses, poems, rhymes and quotes, in their respective memories, so that they can later reproduce them with the highest reliability.

The priest Plato, the Harlot of Athens, argued that it would be a necessary condition, to join his Congregation, for the Doctrine of Faith: “So, let us never include a forgotten soul among those who are sufficiently philosophical for our purposes, but let us seek one with a good memory.”⁶

This created a need for the apprentice to have very sharp discipline during their training, improving, through selected techniques, the memory organization mechanisms in order to store a voluminous amount of information. Added to this was the issue that it was not enough to remember the letters of the texts that were taught orally; it was also necessary to remember the metric of the text, the plot, the rhythm of the prayer, the music, the intonation, because this was required by the gods (Coulanges, 2006).

When the priest prepared public ceremonies, whether funeral or ordinary, he had the obligation to follow exactly the entire set of expressions he had learned. The words, the sounds, the gestures, all of them, had to follow an ordinary rigor, under penalty of tarnishing the entire ritual and thereby attracting divine wrath upon Polis.

Likewise, it was the poet who recited the stories of national heroes and gods; it was not enough to be eloquent, he had to convince, through oratory, take the people to a state of ecstasy, through his speech: for the great Greek enlighteners, the sophists, the persuasive word had as its objective not only to seek the truths, however it would aim at any immediate interest of man: for this reason they call themselves psychogues, those who direct the soul.

reliably remember the deeds of the hero or god being worshiped, and cannot forget important deeds about the person being honored during his presentation.

This was a resource widely used by great orators and rhetoricians when they went to the battlefield to motivate warriors so that they would fight, giving their lives for the country and the cause. A whole set of actions carried out by the great men of history were evoked, how

⁶PLATO. *The Republic*, 486d 1: “Then let's never include a forgetful soul among those who are sufficiently philosophical for our purposes, but look for one with a good memory.”

these warriors had defeated their opponents, fighting even in extremely adverse conditions and that the secret to guaranteeing their success was not simply fighting to win, but fighting not to win. dying, which would mean not being forgotten by friends and still being remembered by subsequent generations, through different means.

When the world becomes divided between those who hold power and those who do not, memory becomes glory and disgrace in a reciprocal manner, especially at a time when the technique of writing was not yet known, in which all the old formulas were expressed orally and stored in memory.

It becomes an unimaginable complication, because it is not possible to measure it, calculate it or even know how much a given individual has the power to retain memories and furthermore, someone's mnemonic capacity can be falsified by themselves, never exalted, because excess can be detected, but amnesia cannot be verified, in its veracity condition. Hence, since very ancient times, priests have recommended the practice of torture, to extract the truth about what the victim actually remembers of their sadism [or their fear, to be more precise.

Memory played a preponderant role in all senses in the arts, ranging from the poetic arts, through the war arts to the political arts, of governance. The aedo and the rhapsode needed to remember the texts, the rhymes, the phonetics and the total musicality of the work, because otherwise it would not be able to move its audience, it would not attract the attention of the spectators and, logically, it would not remain in the memory of the people. In the arts of war, it was an indispensable factor, because the ability to record in memory the maps and access locations of your enemies or the best invasion route or escape for allied soldiers.

Memory and rhetoric have always gone together, because every good speaker and rhetorician must automatically have a high degree of mnemonic capacity, which he generally does, because when preparing for an oral presentation, a rigorous argument, he must memorize, not just excerpts, but a whole collection of works and the respective contexts [semantic, epistemic, philosophical, sociological, syntactic] in which they are found, as well as how they can weave a decent connected dialogue with the present reality.

In the Ancient Age, the issue related to good memory was as valued as it was feared, because an individual who had an admirable capacity for remembering was chosen from a very early age to enter the religious world, because he could respond to the desires of reciting the old sacred formulas. without problems, and this was a concern of the priests, because the gods were angry, unreliable, with a very volatile mood, they were irritated by very little that didn't please them, and they were not creatures with whom men could count on their friendship. , absolutely.

On the other hand, the priests lived in fear that their gods would abandon them, being conquered by the formulas recited by some other individual. Thus, when, even by accident, someone heard the sacred chants and canonical recitals, their tongue was cut out, so that they could not repeat them or tell anyone else. Later, when writing appeared, those who were chosen to serve in the temples, in addition to having their tongues cut out, poured melted lead into their ears, so that they could not hear the songs, prayers and, thus, reproduce them (MARROU , nineteen ninety).

In the work of Alexandre Dumas (1482-1550 AD), *The Count of Monte Cristo* , Edmond Dantès (the hero of the plot) acquires for himself a slave who would be murdered, after his executioners cut out his tongue. This practice, which according to Western Judeo-Christian morality is barbaric and bizarre , is a demonstration that he did not trust anyone, as he could run the risk of being betrayed, having his secret plans revealed to his enemies.

The condition used by Dantès is very far from that of the *priests* of Antiquity, even because the purposes to which the Hero of Dumas dedicated himself was revenge and the ancient priests were a matter of life and death for an entire society, because their The gods had no mercy against a buffoon who defied the sacred rite, destroying the entire city and all its inhabitants. This fear of divine wrath, which did not spare any innocent person, was what justified the existence of such a condition of violence against supposed geniuses endowed with remarkable mnemonic capacity.

the Jester was created, who was a clever man, who in addition to disguising himself as mentally ill, intellectually disabled, *pretended* ⁷forgetting everything he heard and even what he said.

This observance of details, which reveal an absurd fear of the power of memory, points to an understanding of what it represents; a dual, paradoxical figure, not subject to exact control and that places many situations and individuals in the midst of conflicts that exceed their positions, sometimes not as relevant as one might believe due to the dimension of the action to combat the supposed challenge, which is it was about knowing what the individual had heard and what he had kept in his thoughts.

The evocation of memory is a complex artifice, because when good memories are evoked, the bad ones come with them and when memory is denied the potential to evoke terrible

⁷ The *jester* originated in the Byzantine Empire, and at the end of the Crusades it became a common figure in European courts. Today, it is also used as an expression to refer to someone with silly, laughable attitudes, who only serves to distract and amuse, who doesn't take anything seriously. The idea of the jester is currently seen in a pejorative way, as someone without substance or seriousness.

and painful passages of life, it is also denied fair passages of love. and happiness. Only to men endowed with the highest degree of value, like those who developed religion in the Ancient Age, who strived to use their memories to take revenge on adversaries, or eliminate potential rivals, using old sacred formulas.

Apprentices, from a very early age, were trained to record long prayers in their memory and the teaching was in the sense that they repeated, depending on the order learned, following the entire ritual and if they did not do so in the rigors dictated by the master, they would be flogged, because it was said that the apprentices' ears were located on their backs (MARROU, 1990). The fear of severe punishment being applied to them made them listen, record and repeat the formulas in an unblemished and perfect way, because this was what sacred worship and the gods required (COULANGES, 2004).

The doctrine was severe and followed rigorous principles, leaving no room for the student to deviate from it, or to create any line beyond what was traditionally drawn by religious culture and ancestors.

This zeal in remaining faithful to the principles of tradition and culture and punishing, in an exemplary way, anyone who could represent any type of danger to the maintenance of political order, it was because the extent of the potential of the mnemonic capacity of each citizen and ally was not known To this was the insecurity with which everyone lived in relation to their domestic gods and *demons* . Men feared their volatile moods, a situation that led the people of the Ancient Age to overvalue memory, because the rites had to obey an immaculate and impeccable rhythmic meter, together with the rhetoric, because the priest or the sacred singer had to express It was done orally, in an impeccable way, because sacred worship required it.

MEMORY AND RHETORIC IN THE ANCIENT AGE

There was a direct relationship between memory and rhetoric in the ancient Age, in which individuals practiced their speeches for hours on end, not only to remember the texts , but to refine the forms of linguistic expression. This is the most interesting thing you can think of when it comes to studies on memory and the application of acquired and/or developed knowledge about reality, because each word expressed is the product of a fine search, carried out in the human brain and not only by singular words or sounds, such as intonation appropriate to the situation, accompanied by an analytical study of the situation and the public's behavior in response.

It turns out that it was by paying attention to these subtleties that great names in rhetoric came to be remembered, some due to their processes of individual overcoming than due to their speeches, although this is confusing, because in the Ancient and Classical Age only the great rhetoricians were remembered, the others were despised, as someone who was not worthy of being part of cultural memory. There is the case of Demosthenes (799-737 aH), brought to the fore for his unparalleled eloquent capacity, as well as for overcoming his natural disability: there is a report about him suffering from paraphasia, however he dedicated himself to overcoming this difficulty, That's why he trained for years with pebbles in his mouth in order to control his speech. After so much dedication he became an exponent rhetorician. The focus must turn in the direction of knowing how these geniuses reached the state of overcoming their natural weaknesses; Furthermore, it would be interesting to know what types of mnemonic exercises, as well as physical ones, that they underwent until they achieved excellence in the respective field of speech; because it was not enough to speak or express oneself well; it was necessary to move, to persuade the assembly in the middle of the agora.

Rhetoric can be understood, roughly speaking, as the art of speaking extemporaneously; however, it is not about improvising a topic; but, of knowing how to speak eloquently in the midst of situations in which there is no prior preparation condition, because the topic to be discussed had not been put before the citizen in advance. Rhetoric can also be understood as the art (as a technique) of speaking well, with elegance and intonation, respecting the principles of orality and grammar of the vernacular language.

The priest Plato, the Harlot of Athens, considered rhetoric as an evil to be combatted, as it did not work with Truth, but only with opinions. This positioning will be modified later, since in his monologue *Phaedrus* he wanted to create a rhetoric capable of amplifying the Truth.

A position contrary to the Platonic one can be found in the priest Aristotle, the Egotatra, who said that rhetoric could reach the truth, as long as persuasion was based on evidence.

When dealing with rhetoric, Aristotle is more pragmatic than Plato, however he does not stray too far from the Platonic *Phaedrus*; on the contrary, he wishes to continue the arguments of this dialogue, however he did not accept Plato's position when defending that it was an empirical art (technique) and a flattery. For Aristotle, rhetoric is first and foremost an art, an episteme. In this sense, he does not accept that there are two types of rhetoric, but rather the use that does not comply with conventions.

For Oliver Reboul (1998), the function of rhetoric is to persuade, to convince through argument, so much so that he gives it this definition, already making it clear that it is so, that is, the function and the concept are defined in the same matter. In its conception,

Rhetoric is the art of defending oneself, arguing, in situations in which demonstration is not possible, which forces it to go through *common notions*, which are not vulgar opinions, but what each person can find through their common sense, in domains in which nothing would be less scientific than demanding scientific answers. [...] It is the art of finding everything that is persuasive in a case, whenever there is no other resource than contradictory debate (REBOUL, 1998, p. 27).

Rhetoric adds a need for the individual to have intellectual capacity, according to which he has the cognitive conditions to formulate a speech that serves to defend, at the same time he can elaborate arguments against the thesis that he defended before. This faculty should be practiced at the same speed as thinking about linguistic strategies to counter your opponent ; If your words are not enough , your body posture must represent a powerful argument in disarming, defending and attacking your interlocutor, who will represent an enemy to be defeated, to be convinced of your masterful truth.

Generally, a good rhetorician, those who arouse emotions and enchantment wherever and on those who watch them in action in a fierce debate, are great strategists who use their opponents ' arguments against themselves, mainly, seeking to counterattack their flawed arguments, in gaps left by their cultural values, which come to the surface in moments when the defense is not manned, or when a vital point has been attacked. It is an art of intellectual-linguistic-empirical warfare, in which whether the arguments are valid or invalid has little or no interest in the objective of defeating the opponent; arguments must represent the power to awaken the pathetic in the listener who, based on the reactions of the gladiators through words , will start to assume a more or less favorable stance towards one or the other, being convinced by the strategies of arguing and not by adherence to validity of your arguments.

All this just shows the high level of preparation to which the rhetor is and must be subjected, in order to be able to decide to venture into an open debate, especially those in which things of extreme value are disputed, such as political situations and in particular the issue of the right to freedom, in our country, where defense and prosecution lawyers (Prosecutors) fight to convince the jury of the accused's guilt.

In classic times of jurisprudence, the dispute occurred in an attempt to save a life and not just the life of the accused whom they defended or accused. Rhetoric would have to be based on vernacular verbal aesthetics, on a formal allocation of words in order to not only convince about your line of reasoning, but also enchant the public about the idea carried out, in the argument, which was more of a public spectacle of rhetoric, against the backdrop of the trial of someone who had been accused of committing a crime.

Generally, rhetorical clashes are classic and memorable, not only for their mutual expression who show themselves at a high level and with fine preparation of proportionality and respect for the opponent, as well as the elegance of movements duly coordinated to show the power of defense and attack of each litigating party, because every action counts for and against the rhetorical debaters. Therefore, they must have the ability to speak well, with intonation, emphasis, confidence, demonstration of mastery of the subject on which their speech is based and power in placing their arguments.

This is how it should be, because “rhetoric aims to create and elaborate speeches with persuasive purposes” (ARISTÓTELES, 2005). Based on this perception, rhetoric is placed in a singular delimited space, depriving it of any type of broad discussion other than the technical ideal of persuading the listener, about a truth that behaves in a peremptory manner, in the speaker's expressions. .

This clarifies that rhetoric aims at a particular type of action of complex thought, being of a practical, pragmatic nature, very difficult to think about ways of studying and preparing an apprentice, because in addition to being very skilled in dealing with words must be studious to the extreme of knowledge, which would allow him to make broad connections, developing a unique ability to search for speeches, thoughts, jargon, unusual situations, stories and other precise actions that ensure that the rhetorician does not get lost in daydreams and beat your opponent in the field of verbal dispute.

The rhetorician must be well trained so that, when faced with an opponent better prepared than him and more capable, he does not get distracted and end up transforming the high-level intellectual debate into demagoguery and long-winded conversations, meaningless things without the slightest possibility, to arouse public interest . It is necessary to clarify that, for high-level conversations, rhetoric is not necessary; science must be used, because rhetoric serves exclusively to convince. If it made use of proofs as Aristotle of Stagira wanted, it would be science. It is necessary to have the attitude to recognize that there is someone more qualified and who prepared more and better for the game of words that awaited him and this only highlights the constant need to study the thinking and tactics that the opponent has the habit of using. use and to do so, it doesn't matter if it is a speaker or a group that you have to face. Ideally, when giving a lecture with open questions to the public, one should analyze and interpret the dimension of the political-philosophical thought of this group, understanding that group psychology changes greatly when compared to the positioning of the individual against another in which the debate will remain at the level of each person presenting, defending and refuting other people's ideas, at the same time, placing and defending their own. Therefore, it

is a card game in which the slightest perception of what is stated must already be subject to interpretation and return with the aim of persuading the opponent to understand the object analyzed, highlighting that the aim is only to convince and persuasion, when there is no evidence about what you are saying.

The interesting thing about rhetoric is the premise that it must respect the broad contradiction, because since it is a heavy and fierce debate between two powers, both with clear and direct intentions of convincing their listeners, because neither party has knowledge about what you are defending, whether it is someone's guilt or innocence, all parties involved have the right to deliberately position themselves on the issue, arguing, through theories and all the expertise in destroying the argument presented by the rival it must remain at the level of rhetorical strategy, where relegation to the level of mediocrity and offense against the rival's person is not permitted. Therefore, it is the theater of the ridiculous, in which the parties involved in the debate defend what they suppose to be true, in accordance with their most particular interests and their conventions.

In Antiquity, there was strict and careful observance of this posture, because being a great orator and a great rhetorician represented an unparalleled privilege, therefore, none of them desired or wanted to risk having their images tarnished by a slip in their postures as great masters. and debaters.

An aspect to be linked to rhetoric, in Antiquity, and that has survived to the present day, in a certain way, is the issue of beauty, in which beauty was linked to truth, especially in the condition of convincing the public. For the Greeks of the Classical Era, beauty represents goodness and, by extension, represents truth, understanding that, for them, truth meant memory and people tend to remember for longer what is, aesthetically, beautiful; Therefore, if beauty is good, what a beautiful rhetorician says can only be good.

The ideal of Greek man was aesthetic life (*kalokagatía* , *kalo* = beautiful; *agatés* = good), so they admitted that everything that was beautiful was good: now, it is possible to understand, why the honest Greek citizens attacked the priest Socrates, the Libidinous, since he was ugly; therefore all that came out of his mouth were ugly things; therefore, they could only be perverse, bad.

It must be clarified that rhetoric is not a science; it is a persuasion technique in the midst of a fierce debate between two personalities, who present themselves as authorities on something, on a certain subject, demonstrated through theoretical argumentation. No sensible human being will waste his capacity for analysis and synthesis against a buffoon, because this is something ridiculous to even think about. Therefore, what we have is that this is a technique

used excessively by two buffoons, each trying to assert their ego over their opponent. It is common to think of rhetoric as a technique used by great men, which could be a mistake, as it is used more by buffoons, since they ignore science and its discoveries.

It is a game of discussion that is at the level of intellectual chess, anticipating moves and certain that the next step could be the destination for checkmate. It is not a dispute that aims to determine who is right or wrong, it is the determination of the conviction of those watching the debate, as a rhetor will always value presenting himself for a duel in front of a selected audience, with a high capacity for criticism and of abstract thinking.

When we refer to criticism here, the thought expressed means that it means a secular, public, broad, open question that aims to expand operational, tacit and strategic knowledge about a given concept/problem/problem/paradigm. Of course, as a technique, it can be analyzed, studied, improved, perfected in its tactics and performance presented by the debater. The challenges posed are to overcome the opponent in the field of dialectics and convince the public of the idea launched.

The priest Plato, the Harlot of Athens, first used the term *rhetoric* (*Techné Logon*⁸) in his dialogue *Gorgias*, in order to identify the activity carried out by this sophist. In this book he presents it as a political speech intended to flatter. This technique It has a broad development, starting from the 5th century BC as a result of the trust that *logos* provides. It developed in this period due to democracy, in which political power is conquered by word and not by belonging to a noble family.

Rhetoric, which the Greeks identified with the goddess Peithós, is concerned with the persuasive aspects of the word⁹: the rhetorician must be prepared in such a way that he can argue both for and against a given subject.

The first reports about him date back to the fall of the tyrants Gélon and Hierão of Syracuse, as it was with the restoration of democracy that political differences were resolved through the best argument and no longer by force; In this way, the courts received many cases, which had to be based on a speech, which could convince the magistrates about the validity of the applicant's request. It is in this context that Córax (who understood the word as creating persuasion) and his disciple Tísias emerged¹⁰, who developed rhetoric to such an extent that

⁸Currently, the term rhetoric is synonymous with argumentation. In Latin, the word oratory is used, which can be understood as eloquence.

⁹ARISTOTLE. *Rhetoric*, I 2, 1355 b.

¹⁰His followers were Empedocles of Agrigento, Gorgias of Leontinus and Polus.

they even created manuals and rules for its application in forensic speeches. They were concerned with the syntagmatic aspects of speech, more specifically with the *device* .

Another Greek priest who dedicated himself to studying rhetoric was Aristotle, the Egoatra, who characterized rhetoric as “the ability to discover what is appropriate in each case in order to persuade” (ARISTÓTELES, 2005, p. 95), again, delimiting it to a restricted space of investigation and a given end. Thus, rhetoric can be understood in general as the art (technique) that studies and uses language with the intention of persuading.

These paragraphs already place it as an element of scientific disposition that deeply investigates ways of improving the communicative aspect, a fact that comes closer to the objective planned for this investigation.

What the Stagirite considers to be a simple and direct definition is a condition that requires an impressive speed of thought and processing of received data and feedback in record time, things that can only be achieved by a very high degree of skill. intellectuality, cognition and studies, combined with a powerful motivation for combat, which assumes that the opponent must be someone who deserves the rhetoric's respect, otherwise, there will be no expectation of a worthy clash.

Another point is that if the debate is limited to the topic that one of the participants masters fluently and he challenges someone else to this field, he shows himself to be a perfect imbecile, an immoral wild beast, because in the field in which he is a recognized authority, There is no need to challenge someone, unless you are not so convinced of your truths on the subject. Authorities, *experts* , canonical figures are challenged by others, less sure of their authority, so that they can destroy a guru or make a name for themselves over their defeat. Therefore, rhetoric, since its emergence, does not lend itself to proving what a given being knows about something; he may or may not accept a challenge from someone who has shown himself to be up to it, through other works similar or different to his own and thus, the looms are set up and both fight on a common theme, of social interest, which may be the even if the illustrious investigates, as challenged and not as a challenger, because if that were the case, there would be an inversion of powers, in which the genius is taken for a fraud, an individual unsure of what he knows and of which he is so proud of [*supposedly*] know. The greatest rhetoricians in history were the cruel, vengeful and perfidious (in a word, *Christian*) priests Plato, the Harlot of Athens, and Aristotle, the Egoatra (DAU, 2023).

So, the rhetoric starts from a point where its activity is intended to attract an audience, a show in which the challenges are presented as something memorable, worthy of being watched and worth the effort to be remembered, in which there will be a defeated and a winner,

with cheers, bets, volcanic passion and a lot of direct and indirect clashes, both inside and outside the space of intellectual dispute.

Debaters must have a broad and vast command of the semantic fields of vernacular languages in which they venture to seek expressions of a rhetorical nature; because, if placed in a bizarre way, without being aware of such application and the opponent presents due knowledge, this will result in the ruin of his opponent, placing public opinion against him and his own ego in a fragile condition, a fact that can be shown through of indomitable psychosomatic expressions, even to the most experienced public debater, and which can be a fateful point for a coup de grace in the discussion.

Body posture is something that is greatly explored in rhetoric, as well as the intonation of the voice, the expression of looking and receiving the adversary's gaze. It is an art of intellectual-cognitive warfare in which participants impress with the capacity for theoretical-empirical knowledge that they demonstrate to the public and even to their adversary. It is an art in which very few are known with fluent and autonomous mastery, especially because with audiovisual resources, marketing agents mix such actions leading to interference and mediation.

In Antiquity, when the debater could only make use of his knowledge and understanding of the facts that occurred, the readings carried out, the lectures given by his respective masters, the ability to speak was a point that weighed heavily, with the examples cited, taking into account aimed at awakening the pathetic in the judges and the public.

The condition of memory was also linked to rhetoric due to the need for it to have direct links with the past, with situations that occurred and that the debater needs to seek and bring to the public as an example, in order to awaken their feelings. of passion, horror or even, facilitating the condition of understanding about what is being exposed during the public debate, making it clear that all rhetoric occurs in the public, because with it and through it, the aim is to convince the other.

Thus, memory is an essential factor for the exercise of rhetorical art to be carried out vehemently, and it is not possible for such an action to exist without being able to do without the unconditional support of the former and this has always been the case, since it appears, as a monologue, in religions. archaic, passing through the moment when they become public debates, reaching today, in the classic ways that they present themselves to us.

FRIEDRICH NIETZSCHE'S VIEW ON MEMORY

In the *Second Essay of The Genealogy of Morals*, Friedrich Nietzsche discusses man's ability to forget and the creation of memory: man's ability to make promises is a consequence of education and discipline, for this reason this transformation should be the real problem to be studied.

Forgetting is not a violent ignorance, however it is an active power which provides us with all the experiences that happen to us in life, in this way happiness would be umbilically linked to the ability that man has to forget. Happiness is the happiness of appearance: "Happiness in realization is only possible in the *destruction* of the true, of 'existence', of the beautiful appearance, in the pessimistic destruction of illusion: *in the destruction of even its most beautiful brilliance, the Dionysian happiness is achieved. its peak*" (NIETZSCHE, 2006, p. 5).

Nevertheless, he created memory for himself, which is an *active will* to retain impressions: "In short, man had to become methodical, necessary regularity, both with respect to others and with respect to his own ideas, to stay connected with your own future as a promise"! (NIETZSCHE, 2007, p. 29).

Mnemotechnics was implanted in man through violence, the pedagogy that subjected him to it can be summarized in the maxim: "The letter with blood enters". The creation of memory was done through cruel holocausts (the sacrifice of the firstborn, castrations carried out by religions, which are the most perfect systems of cruelty), because we have known for a long time that pain helps memory. It is here that we find asceticism, whose ideas are fixed in memory to such an extent that they must impede the functioning of the nervous and intellectual system:

Due to similar tragedies, five or six "I don't want to", five or six promises were managed to be fixed in memory, in order to enjoy the advantages of a peaceful society and with these memory aids, one entered into Reason! Oh! Reason, gravity, the control of passions, all this infernal machination called reflection, all the pompous privileges of man, how expensive they were! So much blood and so much dishonor at the bottom of all these 'good things'! (NIETZSCHE, 2007, p. 31-2).

The most general effect of the intellect is illusion; it is a way that the individual found in order to preserve his life, for which the intellect uses dissimulation.

CONCLUSION

Rhetoric and memory make up the human scope and, even though it can be taken into account that they move in independent directions, the bonds of communication and connection make them express conditions inherent to human existence and its entire process of development, mastery and even resolving conflicts that, otherwise, if not resolved, the results would be catastrophic.

It is from there that diplomacy becomes the political element that, currently, is experienced as something of extreme value between nations, even when they are not friends and share the same ideological principles.

In Antiquity, memory represented an element of high value, since there were no storage mechanisms for ideas, maps and architectural and mechanical projects other than in the creator's thoughts.

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